

Medieval Śrīvaiṣṇavism

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Entry tags: Bhakti traditions, Vaiṣṇava Traditions, Religious Group, Pāñcarātra tradition, Hinduism, Indic Religious Traditions

Śrīvaiṣṇavism is a Hindu sect that worships Viṣṇu along with his consort Śrī, the main leader of which is Rāmānuja (traditional dates: 1017-1137), a proponent of viśiṣṭādvaita ('qualified non-dualism'). This tradition is based on ubhaya-vedānta, i.e. both the Sanskrit and the Tamil scriptures. The latter consists essentially of the poetry of the Āḷvārs (Tamil bhakti poets [6th-9th centuries]), collectively known as the Nālāyira Tivviya Pirapantam (or Nālāyira Divya Prabandham), especially Nammāḷvār's Tiruvāymoḷi, which is referred to as the drāviḍa-veda ('Tamil Vedas') or dramīḍopaniṣad ('Tamil Upaniṣad'). Therefore, this sect, while not limited to Southern India, is much more present in that region than elsewhere. Around the 13th-15th centuries, differences of opinions began to rise with its important ācāryas (e.g. Piḷḷai Lokācārya [traditional dates: 1264-1327], Vedānta Deśika [traditional dates: 1268-1369] and Maṇavāla Māmuni [traditional dates: 1370-1445]) interpreting the scriptures differently on a few theological issues. This schism became cristallised a couple of centuries later (around the 18th-19th centuries), leading to the formation of two schools, the Northern (vaṭakalai) and the Southern (teṅkalai) ones. The former follows in the path shown by Vedānta Deśika.

Date Range: 1017 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Tamil Nadu

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India

Tamil Nadu

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Guruparamparāprabhāvam. Āṛāyirappaṭi Guruparamparāprabhāvam. Composed by Piṅṅaḷakiya Perumāḷi Jīyar and edited by Krishnaswami Aiyangar. Triplicane: Cē. Kuruṣṇamācāriar patippu, 1975 [1927].
- Source 2: Chari, S.M. (1978). The Philosophy of Viśiṣṭādvaita Vedānta: A Study Based on Vedānta Deśika's Adhikaraṇa-sārāvalī. Delhi: Motilal Banarasidass Publishers.
- Source 3: Venkatachari, K. K. A. (1978). The Maṇipravāḷa Literature of the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas, 12th to 15th Century A.D. Bombay: Ananthacharya Research Institute.

Notes: Other sources: Mumme, P. Y. (1988). The Śrīvaiṣṇava theological dispute : Maṇavālamāmuni and Vedānta Deśika. Madras : New Era Publications. Raman, S. (2007). Self-Surrender (Prapatti) to God in Śrīvaiṣṇavism: Tamil Cats or Sanskrit Monkeys? New York: Routledge. Appadurai, A. (2008). Worship and conflict under colonial rule: A South Indian case. Cambridge [England: Cambridge University Press. McCann, E. (2016). Ācāryābhimāna: Agency, ontology, and salvation in Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Śrīvacana Bhūṣaṇa (Doctoral dissertation, McGill University). Retrieved from eScholarship@McGill.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.philtar.ac.uk/encyclopedia/hindu/devot/vatak.html>
- Source 1 Description: An encyclopaedic entry
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.academia.edu/Documents/in/Srivai%E1%B9%A3%E1%B9%87avism>
- Source 2 Description: Academia articles on this religious group
- Source 3 URL: https://www.academia.edu/Documents/in/Visi_advaita_Vedanta
- Source 3 Description: Very similar to the previous

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://sadagopan.org/>
- Source 1 Description: A Śrīvaiṣṇava repository for mainly Vaṭakalai works with traditional interpretation/translation of the texts
- Source 2 URL: <http://acharya.org/d.html>
- Source 2 Description: Again, another traditional source of texts.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Śrīvaiṣṇavas consider as their scriptures both the Vedas (which are in Sanskrit) and the the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham, a collection of the Aḷvār poet-saints' 4000 songs in Tamil, which they consider as the drāviḍa-veda, or the Tamil Vedas.

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: There are some works which are considered as scriptures that have been written down (presumably later), like the works of some ācāryas, e.g. Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Śrīvacanabhūṣaṇam or Vedānta Deśika's Rahasyatrayasāram. But both the Vedas and the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham are thought to have been recited/sung and then orally transmitted before being written down.

Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: As pointed out in the previous reply, both the Vedas and the "Tamil Vedas" are thought to be revelations that came out through the mouths of select people, and they were later orally transmitted before being written down (in the case of the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham for example).

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

— Yes

Notes: The Vedas, believed to be eternal, are said to have been revealed to a few ascetics. The Tamil Veda, especially the Tiruvāymoḷi by Nammālvār, is said to have been inspired by God. For more details on this see Anandakichenin, Suganya. Nālāyirativiyappirapantam (Nālāyiradivya Prabandham). In: Jain P., Sherma R., Khanna M. (eds). Hinduism and Tribal Religions. Encyclopedia of Indian Religions. Dordrecht: Springer (2018) and Anandakichenin, Suganya. Nammālvār. In: Jain P., Sherma R., Khanna M. (eds). Hinduism and Tribal Religions. Encyclopedia of Indian Religions. Dordrecht: Springer (2018). There is also a story about how the Divya Prabandham was lost and the retrieved thanks to the intervention of Nāthamuni, who was helped by Nammālvār (who had passed away by then), who revealed not just his own works, but also those of the other Ālvārs.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

— No

Notes: The Vedas are said to be eternal, just like God, hence not composed by Him. Inspired ascetics had hymns appear in their minds. The Tamil Vedas were inspired by God, but they came through a human poet (albeit considered to be an incarnation of Nārāyaṇa's commander-in-chief, Viśvaksena).

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

— No

↳ Inspired by high god:

— Yes

Notes: the Divya Prabandham was. Please see the answers to the previous subquestions.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

— No

Notes: NB: The Tiruvāymoḷi, which is the core of the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham and which is considered as the Tamil Veda, was brought into this world through Nammālvār, who though a human, is thought to have been a reincarnation of Nārāyaṇa's commander-in-chief, Viśvaksena (=a supernatural being).

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

— Yes

Notes: Nammālvār, as well as the other Ālvār, whose collective works are known as the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham, are said to be human incarnations of various nityasūris, i.e. eternally free souls that live and serve Nārāyaṇa in His heavenly abode, Vaikuṅṭha. For further information on this, please see Anandakichenin, Suganya. Ālvār. In: Jain P., Sherma R., Khanna M. (eds). Hinduism and Tribal Religions. Encyclopedia of Indian Religions. Dordrecht: Springer (2018).

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent, yes, for the Tamil Vedas: the poets who composed the poems that make up the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham were after all humans by birth, despite being incarnations of divine beings.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The scriptures are not to be tampered with, nor the ideas found in them interpreted as per the will of the individual.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Hagiographic texts as well as commentaries on the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham (12th c. onwards) mention assemblies where specialists debate on the correct interpretation of key topics.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

Notes: It is only educated and acknowledged scholars who have that power.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: As pointed out earlier on, interpreting or revisiting interpretations are the realm of acknowledged scholars, often ācāryas, who are officially sanctioned figures.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on what needs to be transmitted, it is the ācārya who transmits esoteric scriptures. As for the Divya Prabandham, anyone who can recite it can transmit to the others.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: We can mention here both the Vedas and the Divya Prabandham. The recitation of both scriptures are codified, both at home and in public places such as the temple.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Quite a few Vedic (Śaivism) and non-Vedic (Jainism, Islam) "religions" co-existed during that

period of time. Although not to be blindly trusted, the hagiographic text Guruparamparāprabhāvam (13th-14th c.) by Piṅṅaḷakiya Perumāḷ Jīyar mentions various interactions with people of other faiths. Rāmānuja, for example, is said to have participated in theological debates with 12000 Jains and conquered them [Guruparamparāprabhāvam, chapter: "Iḷaiyālvār vaibhavam").

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

— Yes

Notes: The cultural contact with other faiths is almost always competitive. As pointed out in the notes to the previous question, hagiographic texts mention theological debates between scholars of other faiths and the Śrīvaiṣṇava Ācāryas like Rāmānuja. For example, Rāmānuja, allegedly in exile due to the persecution of a Śaiva Chola king, is said to have argued against the Jains in Toṅṅaṅūr in modern-day Karnataka, conquered them and brought them to his fold. Vedānta Deśika is said to have debated against the Advaitins to establish the precepts of viśiṣṭādvaita. He even composed a book called Śatadūṣaṇi to enumerate his objections to Advaita.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— No

Notes: The Ācāryas see the other religions as belonging to one of the two categories: 1) the [veda-]bāhya: those that are "outside" the Vedas, i.e. those who do not accept the authority of the Vedas, and 2) the kuḍṛṣṭi one: those who do accept the authority of the Vedas, but have a "twisted view" of them, e.g. the Advaitins. Therefore, the cultural contact is not really accommodating, which is proven by the mention of numerous religious debates among them [e.g. Guruparamparāprabhāvam, chapter "Iḷaiyālvār vaibhavam".

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— No

Notes: Because of the above-mentioned reasons, the cultural contact is hardly ever neutral. In fact, later on, there will be a friction even within the Śrīvaiṣṇava community itself, which means that such neutrality becomes scarce even among the later followers of Rāmānuja.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Yes

Notes: Again, we have to rely on hagiographies such as Garuḍavāhana Paṅḍita's Divyasūricaritam (11th or 12th century [?]) for answering this question, although the historians find it hard to (dis)prove it: a hard-to-identify Chola king called Kṛmikaṅṅha is said to have persecuted the Śrīvaiṣṇavas and tried to make Rāmānuja proclaim Śiva's superiority in writing. At this, Rāmānuja is claimed to have fled the region and exiled himself in the modern-day Karnataka for twelve years. For a brief discussion on this topic, see Whitney Cox. Politics, Kingship and Poetry in Medieval South India: Moonset on Sunrise Mountain. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016, p. 241n55.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— Yes

Notes: Hagiographic texts such as the Guruparamparāprabhāvam and temple chronicles such as the Śrīraṅgam ones, known as the Kōyil Oḷuku (compiled between the 14th and the 18th centuries) mention at least two waves of Muslim invasions (from Delhi), followed by the looting of the temples and the killing of the Śrīvaiṣṇavas who offered resistance. The stories of how Malik Kafur attacked Śrīraṅgam and killed several priests (including Sudarśana Sūri, the author of Śrutaparakāśikā), how some, like Vedānta Deśika, had to lie among corpses to survive the murderous assault, and how others, like Piḷḷai Lokācārya, organized themselves to save the utsava-bera (the processional icon) and walked hundreds of miles with the icon to keep it safe, are narrated in detail in these works. For a brief historical description of the invasion, see K.V. Raman. Sri Varadarajaswami Temple, Kanchi: A Study of Its History, Art and Architecture. New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 2003, p.24.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: NB: Further research is required in the field. Temples are built according to rules of architecture prescribed for a larger community of Vedic believers, with specialized rules and rituals for the Śrīvaiṣṇava ones, but it is not clear if this group itself built temples. Maṭhas (roughly, monasteries), resting places for Vaiṣṇava travellers (Rāmānucakūṭams) are also built, although they cannot be called "monumental." Deceased ācāryas have their mortal remains buried and a small structure (known as a tiruvaracu or br̥ndāvanam) with a shrine built upon. The place is worshipped by the disciples and other Śrīvaiṣṇavas.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not have reliable data on this. Further research is required in the field.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: There is an initiation ceremony for those wishing to become a Śrīvaiṣṇava. Rāmānuja himself is said to have undergone it [Guruparamparāprabhāvam, chapter "Iḷaiyālvār vaibhavam"]. It is known as samāśrayaṇam or pañcasamskāra ('five sacraments'): 1) tāpam - the branding of the impressions of Nārāyaṇa's weapons, the discus and the conch, on either side of the upper arms; 2) [ūrdhva-]puṇḍram - the wearing of the vertical marks that are supposed to resemble Nārāyaṇa's feet, on twelve different parts of the body, including the forehead; 3) dāśya-nāma: the disciple is given a new name, often "Rāmanuja" or any of Nārāyaṇa's names, to which the suffix "dāsa" or "servant of" is added; 4) mantra: the disciple is given three sacred mantras; 5) iḷyā: the disciple is taught how to worship Nārāyaṇa properly. For more details on this topic, see Chari, S.M. Vaiṣṇavism: Its Philosophy, Theology, and Religious Discipline. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishers, 1994, pp.306-312.

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: It is not enough to be born in a Śrīvaiṣṇava family. One ought to become one by getting initiated.

Assigned by personal choice:

– No

Notes: Technically-speaking, the ācāryas cannot choose who and how to initiate, but accept anyone who sincerely seeks initiation and perform the appropriate rites.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Class is no deterrent at all. Not even caste is a deterrent in this belief system. For example, the Guruparamparāprabhāvam mentions that Rāmānuja had non-Brahmin disciples (e.g. Piḷḷai Uṟaṅkā Villitācar). Before him, Yāmunācārya is said to have had a fourth-caste disciple, Māṟṅṅēri Nampī, for whom Periya Nampī, a Brahmin disciple of Yāmunācārya and one of Rāmānuja's ācāryas, is said to have performed the last rites.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There are no age restrictions.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Gender is no bar for being a Śrīvaiṣṇava either. Rāmānuja himself is said to have had female disciples, like Tirunakari Piḷḷai. A later ācārya, Nampīḷḷai, seems to have taught the Tiruvāymoḷi to a female disciple (among others) called Tirukkōṅṅēri Dāsyai, who wrote a short commentary on it.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Please see the answer to the main question. The initiatory rites called samāśrayaṇam or pañcasaṃskāram are an absolute necessity to become a Śrīvaiṣṇava, and therefore, for attaining moksha (liberation) itself.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Notes: A devoted disciple approaching a qualified ācārya for the sake of initiation is the only requirement.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Please see previous answer.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not have reliable data on this. Further research is required in the field.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: According to hagiographic texts such as the Guruparamparāprabhāvam, conversions are made following debates, at the end of which the defeated embrace the creed of the winner. But although public debates and discourses may have been common, it is not clear how active or aggressive proselytization was.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: "Mandated" is probably not the right word here. Part of the role of the religious professionals is to show the "right" path to everyone, which means getting people to the Śrīvaiṣṇava fold. And this is why hagiographic and other texts mention public debates, which, if won, had the defeated embrace the other faith. But it is not clear if the ācāryas, who also conducted public discourses, were deliberately sent out with a mission to conquer the others. The aim is to communicate the beliefs to those who wished for them.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: "Mandated" is definitely not the word here. Adherents could bring people of their acquaintance to an ācārya so that they can get initiated (willingly), but I am yet to come across a text that mentions proselytizing as mandatory for all adherents.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Please see the answer for the first subquestion in this field. The ācāryas do have "missionary" work, as they travel from one place to another, as per the laws that the "Hindu" sanyāsins ("the renunciators") abide in general. This is a means to--although not only meant for this--accomplish their mission to educate and possibly convert people from different regions.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Please see previous answers.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

Notes: It is hard to say "yes" or "no" to this question. The hagiographic texts do say that people who were cured of some misfortune (like a Jain king's possessed daughter who was cured by applying the water that was used to wash Rāmānuja's feet) or were vanquished in a verbal debate voluntarily came to the Śrīvaiṣṇava fold. Whether proselytization was systematically coercive is hard to say.

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– No

Notes: From what we know from the hagiographic texts, no. Historical records are scarce and do not seem to document physical force being used by the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas.

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Notes: Such a thing is not recorded anywhere, to my knowledge, at least not during the default period.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but only sometimes. We know that for example a few Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas and maṭhas were in good terms with the Vijayanagara empire (1336-1646). But hagiography mentioned how Rāmānuja was persecuted by a Chola king of Śaiva persuasion, but later on, he got the patronage of a king in modern-day Karnataka. So this is not a categorical yes.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: it could be, especially in the temples established by kings, who would make provisions for the running of the temple and its various activities, like the singing of hymns. The Śrīraṅgam temple chronicles (which is not to be trusted as unadulterated historical truth) enumerates the kings who renovated or constructed different parts of the temple, and who lavishly donated money for its maintenance and the conducting of various rites inter alia. But not not all temples were systematically favoured, nor all priests were paid by polity.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Please see previous answer.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The heads of the religion are sanyāsins, who have renounced worldly pleasures, and do not have an official political role, except perhaps as the king's ācārya.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: Political officials are definitely not equivalent to religious officials. They have clearly distinct roles.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not have any record of that, to my knowledge, especially for this time period.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There might be some overlapping, especially when it comes to moral codes, but otherwise legal and religious codes are separate and serve different purposes.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to say, as it depends on specific kings and specific time periods. During the Vijayanagara period, some Śrīvaiṣṇava monasteries are said to have been favoured with preferential treatment, which might include economic favours like tax exemptions.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography is well developed, as God in His iconic form is very important for the worship of humans. Arcā (or "image") is one of God's five forms, and ācāryas like Piḷḷai Lokācārya believe that once an icon is made, it is verily God's body, not to be thought in terms of the material it was made of.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

Notes: Homes have altars for private worship; temples are public places where elaborate worship of the image of God and His people is made.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Icons of Nārāyaṇa and His entourage are represented like full-fledged human beings (but not just), with added divine features, like extra arms. Eyes are an important feature on the face of the Deity.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is worshipped in His half-lion, half-man form (Narasimha), in His boar and other such forms. His vehicle, Garuḍa the eagle, is also worshipped in the temples.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

— Yes

Notes: Most natural elements (like mountain, rain, etc.) have a deity as their spirit, and this is not specific to Śrīvaiṣṇava belief, which simply claims that they all have Nārāyaṇa as their Master.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

— Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is represented as having a human form (except when He appears as an animal), plus distinguishing features like a pair of extra arms. The same goes for His entourage (i.e. His wives, servants, etc.).

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

— Yes

Notes: God is all-pervasive, so all places and things can be a reference to Him. Like the number 26.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

— Yes

Notes: Many Śrīvaiṣṇava texts, including Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Arcirādi, describe in detail afterlife, i.e. the soul's progress towards Vaikuṅṭha, and also what life is like there. Iconographic representations of this exist now, but it is not clear if they were represented during that period of time.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

— Yes

Notes: One example is the pair of Nārāyaṇa's weapons, the conch and the discus, branded on the devotees upper arms during initiation. There is also the vertical marks made on the forehead (among other places), which represent the feet of Nārāyaṇa.

↳ Humans:

— Yes

Notes: The Lord's human devotees are also represented and worshipped, probably already by Rāmānuja's time. He himself had two of his statues made during his lifetime, according to hagiographic texts such as the Gurupamparāprabhāvam.

↳ Other features of iconography:

— Yes

Notes: There are many features, like Nārāyaṇa is represented as seated, standing or reclining. For more information on this topic, please see Champakalakshmi, R. (1981). Vaiṣṇava iconography in the Tamil country. New Delhi: Orient Longman.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Traditional texts do not mention any case of apostasy. Rāmānuja's cousin (although not yet a Śrīvaiṣṇava during the time the event took place) is said to have embraced Śaivism for a while, but he was brought back to the Vaiṣṇava fold. This is the closest we get to this concept.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: It is hard to say. Initially, this seems like a small religious group, allegedly at war with the ruling monarch who was also a "Hindu" but a Śaiva one (i.e. a group that is said to have been actively suppressed by a larger, politically powerful group). Later on, when the threat seems to come from non-Vedic, or even "non-Indian" religions (e.g. Muslim invasions), this religious group may have been considered as a small religious group seen as being part of a larger "Vedic" group.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Temples are sacred places of public worship; homes also have an altar, which is also sacred. Of special importance are the temples/temple-towns praised by the Āḷvārs in their poetry (those places are known as divyadeśams, or "divine places"), but also places with mythological links, like Dvāraka and Ayodhyā, (allegedly) Kṛṣṇa's and Rāma's birthplaces respectively.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Often the temple is situated by a river, on a hill, or by the ocean. For example, Śrīraṅgam, the most important Śrīvaiṣṇava temple already by Rāmānuja's time, is praised as much as the river Kāveri that surrounds it. Vēṅkaṭam, currently known as Tirumalā-Tirupati, has been another important temple for centuries, and it was built on a hill, which is much praised and revered both by the Āḷvārs and by the ācāryas.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: It is hard to say. While Rāmānuja and the ācāryas in general were considered as leaders, it is hard to say how hierarchy functioned among them. After all, every soul is supposed to be God's body,

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: These leaders are believed to possess divine qualities, like compassion, fortitude, etc. much more than the average human being. Even though their piety may give them supernatural powers (like Rāmānuja was able to exorcise a girl who was possessed), they are described as going about using their powers.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: He can do it if he wants to.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, if the leader happens to pass away without naming anyone as his successor.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: It is not necessarily mentioned in the written texts, but in the case of the Ahobila Maṭha for example, God (in His Narasiṃha form) is said to communicate His choice.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: The ācāryas are supposed to be well-versed in the scriptures and have impeccable behaviour. So they are supposed to be infallible. If they do fail, it is God's problem to punish them,

not the humans'.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Unquestioned obedience to one's ācārya is prescribed.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam and other hagiographic texts mention pilgrimage, and sometimes how people come upon interesting events while on a pilgrimage, e.g. Nāthamuni getting a message to come back and settle in Southern India, or Rāmānuja going as far away as to modern-day Jammu.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: Pilgrimage is important but not necessarily obligatory. The ascetics are supposed not to stay put in one place for more than a few weeks, except during the monsoon, but lay devotees, although encouraged to visit sacred places, are not censured for not doing so.

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Quite a few Vedic (Śaivism) and non-Vedic (Jainism, Islam) "religions" co-existed during that period of time. Although not to be blindly trusted, the hagiographic text Guruparamparāprabhāvam (13th-14th c.) by Piṅgaḷakiya Perumāḷ Jīyar mentions various interactions with people of other faiths. Rāmānuja, for example, is said to have participated in theological debates with 12000 Jains and conquered them [Guruparamparāprabhāvam, chapter: "aiyālvār vaibhavam").

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact with other faiths is almost always competitive. As pointed out in the notes to the previous question, hagiographic texts mention theological debates between scholars of other faiths and the Śrīvaiṣṇava Ācāryas like Rāmānuja. For example, Rāmānuja, allegedly in exile due to the persecution of a Śaiva Chola king, is said to have argued against the Jains in Toṅṅaṅūr in modern-day Karnataka, conquered them and brought them to his fold. Vedānta Deśika is said to have debated against the Advaitins to establish the precepts of viśiṣṭādvaita. He even composed a book called Śatadūṣaṇi to enumerate his objections to Advaita.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The Ācāryas see the other religions as belonging to one of the two categories: 1) the [veda-]bāhya: those that are "outside" the Vedas, i.e. those who do not accept the authority of the Vedas, and 2) the kudṛṣṭi one: those who do accept the authority of the Vedas, but have a "twisted view" of them, e.g. the Advaitins. Therefore, the cultural contact is not really accommodating, which is proven by the mention of numerous religious debates among them [e.g. Guruparamparāprabhāvam, chapter "||aiyālvār vaibhavam".

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Because of the above-mentioned reasons, the cultural contact is hardly ever neutral. In fact, later on, there will be a friction even within the Śrīvaiṣṇava community itself, which means that such neutrality becomes scarce even among the later followers of Rāmānuja.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Again, we have to rely on hagiographies such as Garuḍavāhana Paṇḍita's Divyasūricaritam (11th or 12th century [?]) for answering this question, although the historians find it hard to (dis)prove it: a hard-to-identify Chola king called Kṛmikaṅṭha is said to have persecuted the Śrīvaiṣṇavas and tried to make Rāmānuja proclaim Śiva's superiority in writing. At this, Rāmānuja is claimed to have fled the region and exiled himself in the modern-day Karnataka for twelve years. For a brief discussion on this topic, see Whitney Cox. Politics, Kingship and Poetry in Medieval South India: Moonset on Sunrise Mountain. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016, p. 241n55.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Hagiographic texts such as the Guruparamparāprabhāvam and temple chronicles such as the Śrīraṅgam ones, known as the Kōyil Oḷuku (compiled between the 14th and the 18th centuries) mention at least two waves of Muslim invasions (from Delhi), followed by the looting of the temples and the killing of the Śrīvaiṣṇavas who offered resistance. The stories of how Malik Kafur attacked Śrīraṅgam and killed several priests (including Sudarśana Sūri, the author of Śrutaprakāśikā), how some, like Vedānta Deśika, had to lie among corpses to survive the murderous assault, and how others, like Piḷḷai Lokācārya, organized themselves to save the utsava-bera (the processional icon) and walked hundreds of miles with the icon to keep it safe, are narrated in detail in these works. For a brief historical description of the invasion, see K.V. Raman. Sri Varadarajaswami Temple, Kanchi: A Study of Its History, Art and Architecture. New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 2003, p.24.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: There is an initiation ceremony for those wishing to become a Śrīvaiṣṇava. Rāmānuja himself is said to have undergone it [Guruparamparāprabhāvam, chapter "||aiyālvār vaibhavam"). It is known as samāśrayaṅgam or pañcasaṃskāra ('five sacraments'): 1) tāpam - the branding of the impressions of Nārāyaṇa's weapons, the discus and the conch, on either side of the upper arms; 2) [ūrdhva-]puṇḍram -

the wearing of the vertical marks that are supposed to resemble Nārāyaṇa's feet, on twelve different parts of the body, including the forehead; 3) dāśya-nāma: the disciple is given a new name, often "Rāmaṇuja" or any of Nārāyaṇa's names, to which the suffix "dāśa" or "servant of" is added; 4) mantra: the disciple is given three sacred mantras; 5) ijjā: the disciple is taught how to worship Nārāyaṇa properly. For more details on this topic, see Chari, S.M. *Vaiṣṇavism: Its Philosophy, Theology, and Religious Discipline*. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishers, 1994, pp.306-312.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: It is not enough to be born in a Śrīvaiṣṇava family. One ought to become one by getting initiated.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– No

Notes: Technically-speaking, the ācāryas cannot choose who and how to initiate, but accept anyone who sincerely seeks initiation and perform the appropriate rites.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Class is no deterrent at all. Not even caste is a deterrent in this belief system. For example, the Guruparamparāprabhāvam mentions that Rāmānuja had non-Brahmin disciples (e.g. Piḷḷai Uṟaṅkā Villitācar). Before him, Yāmunācārya is said to have had a fourth-caste disciple, Māṅṅānēri Nampī, for whom Periya Nampī, a Brahmin disciple of Yāmunācārya and one of Rāmānuja's ācāryas, is said to have performed the last rites.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There are no age restrictions.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Gender is no bar for being a Śrīvaiṣṇava either. Rāmānuja himself is said to have had female disciples, like Tirunakari Piḷḷai. A later ācārya, Nampīḷḷai, seems to have taught the Tiruvāymoḷi to a female disciple (among others) called Tirukkōṅṅēri Dāśyai, who wrote a short commentary on it.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Please see the answer to the main question. The initiatory rites called samāśrayaṇam or pañcasamskāram are an absolute necessity to become a Śrīvaiṣṇava, and therefore, for attaining moksha (liberation) itself.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Notes: A devoted disciple approaching a qualified ācārya for the sake of initiation is the only requirement.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: According to hagiographic texts such as the Guruparamparāprabhāvam, conversions are made following debates, at the end of which the defeated embrace the creed of the winner. But although public debates and discourses may have been common, it is not clear how active or aggressive proselytization was.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: "Mandated" is probably not the right word here. Part of the role of the religious professionals is to show the "right" path to everyone, which means getting people to the Śrīvaiṣṇava fold. And this is why hagiographic and other texts mention public debates, which, if won, had the defeated embrace the other faith. But it is not clear if the ācāryas, who also conducted public discourses, were deliberately sent out with a mission to conquer the others. The aim is to communicate the beliefs to those who wished for them.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: "Mandated" is definitely not the word here. Adherents could bring people of their acquaintance to an ācārya so that they can get initiated (willingly), but I am yet to come across a text that mentions proselytizing as mandatory for all adherents.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Please see the answer for the first subquestion in this field. The ācāryas do have "missionary" work, as they travel from one place to another, as per the laws that the "Hindu" sanyāsins ("the renouncers") abide in general. This is a means to--although not only meant for this--accomplish their mission to educate and possibly convert people from different regions.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Please see previous answers.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

Notes: It is hard to say "yes" or "no" to this question. The hagiographic texts do say that people who were cured of some misfortune (like a Jain king's possessed daughter who was cured by

applying the water that was used to wash Rāmānuja's feet) or were vanquished in a verbal debate voluntarily came to the Śrīvaiṣṇava fold. Whether proselytization was systematically coercive is hard to say.

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– No

Notes: From what we know from the hagiographic texts, no. Historical records are scarce and do not seem to document physical force being used by the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas.

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Notes: Such a thing is not recorded anywhere, to my knowledge, at least not during the default period.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but only sometimes. We know that for example a few Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas and maṭhas were in good terms with the Vijayanagara empire (1336-1646). But hagiography mentioned how Rāmānuja was persecuted by a Chola king of Śaiva persuasion, but later on, he got the patronage of a king in modern-day Karnataka. So this is not a categorical yes.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: it could be, especially in the temples established by kings, who would make provisions for the running of the temple and its various activities, like the singing of hymns. The Śrīraṅgam temple chronicles (which is not to be trusted as unadulterated historical truth) enumerates the kings who renovated or constructed different parts of the temple, and who lavishly donated money for its maintenance and the conducting of various rites inter alia. But not all temples were systematically favoured, nor all priests were paid by polity.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Please see previous answer.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The heads of the religion are sanyāsins, who have renounced worldly pleasures, and do not have an official political role, except perhaps as the king's ācārya.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: Political officials are definitely not equivalent to religious officials. They have clearly distinct roles.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not have any record of that, to my knowledge, especially for this time period.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There might be some overlapping, especially when it comes to moral codes, but otherwise legal and religious codes are separate and serve different purposes.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to say, as it depends on specific kings and specific time periods. During the Vijayanagara period, some Śrīvaiṣṇava monasteries are said to have been favoured with preferential treatment, which might include economic favours like tax exemptions.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Traditional texts do not mention any case of apostasy. Rāmānuja's cousin (although not yet a Śrīvaiṣṇava during the time the event took place) is said to have embraced Śaivism for a while, but he was brought back to the Vaiṣṇava fold. This is the closest we get to this concept.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not have reliable data on this. Further research is required in the field.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not have reliable data on this. Further research is required in the field.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: It is hard to say. initially, this seems like a small religious group, allegedly at war with the ruling

monarch who was also a "Hindu" but a Śaiva one (i.e. a group that is said to have been actively suppressed by a larger, politically powerful group). Later on, when the threat seems to come from non-Vedic, or even "non-Indian" religions (e.g. Muslim invasions), this religious group may have been considered as a small religious group seen as being part of a larger "Vedic" group.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: It is hard to say. While Rāmānuja and the ācāryas in general were considered as leaders, it is hard to say how hierarchy functioned among them. After all, every soul is supposed to be God's body,

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: These leaders are believed to possess divine qualities, like compassion, fortitude, etc. much more than the average human being. Even though their piety may give them supernatural powers (like Rāmānuja was able to exorcise a girl who was possessed), they are described as going about using their powers.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: He can do it if he wants to.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, if the leader happens to pass away without naming anyone as his successor.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: It is not necessarily mentioned in the written texts, but in the case of the Ahobila Maṭha for example, God (in His Narasiṃha form) is said to communicate His choice.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: The ācāryas are supposed to be well-versed in the scriptures and have impeccable behaviour. So they are supposed to be infallible. If they do fail, it is God's problem to punish them, not the humans'.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Unquestioned obedience to one's ācārya is prescribed.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Śrīvaiṣṇavas consider as their scriptures both the Vedas (which are in Sanskrit) and the the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham, a collection of the Aḷvār poet-saints' 4000 songs in Tamil, which they consider as the drāviḍa-veda, or the Tamil Vedas.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: There are some works which are considered as scriptures that have been written down (presumably later), like the works of some ācāryas, e.g. Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Śrīvacanabhūṣaṇam or Vedānta Deśika's Rahasyatrayasāram. But both the Vedas and the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham are thought to have been recited/sung and then orally transmitted before being written down.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: As pointed out in the previous reply, both the Vedas and the "Tamil Vedas" are thought to be revelations that came out through the mouths of select people, and they were later orally transmitted before being written down (in the case of the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham for example).

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Vedas, believed to be eternal, are said to have been revealed to a few ascetics. The Tamil Veda, especially the Tiruvāymoḷi by Nammālvār, is said to have been inspired by God. For more details on this see Anandakichenin, Suganya. Nālāyirativiyappirapantam (Nālāyiradivya Prabandham). In: Jain P., Sherma R., Khanna M. (eds). Hinduism and Tribal Religions. Encyclopedia of Indian Religions. Dordrecht: Springer (2018) and Anandakichenin, Suganya. Nammālvār. In: Jain P., Sherma R., Khanna M. (eds). Hinduism and Tribal Religions. Encyclopedia of Indian Religions. Dordrecht: Springer (2018). There is also a story about how the Divya Prabandham was lost and the retrieved thanks to the intervention of Nāthamuni, who was helped by Nammālvār (who had passed away by then), who revealed not just his own works, but also those of the other Ālvārs.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Notes: The Vedas are said to be eternal, just like God, hence not composed by Him. Inspired ascetics had hymns appear in their minds. The Tamil Vedas were inspired by God, but they came through a human poet (albeit considered to be an incarnation of Nārāyaṇa's commander-in-chief, Viśvaksena).

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: the Divya Prabandham was. Please see the answers to the previous subquestions.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: NB: The Tiruvāymoḷi, which is the core of the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham and which is considered as the Tamil Veda, was brought into this world through Nammālvār, who though a human, is thought to have been a reincarnation of Nārāyaṇa's commander-in-chief, Viśvaksena (=a supernatural being).

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Nammālvār, as well as the other Ālvār, whose collective works are known as the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham, are said to be human incarnations of various nityasūris, i.e. eternally free souls that live and serve Nārāyaṇa in His heavenly abode, Vaikuṅṭha. For further information on this, please see Anandakichenin, Suganya. Ālvār. In: Jain P., Sherma R., Khanna M. (eds). Hinduism and Tribal Religions. Encyclopedia of Indian Religions. Dordrecht: Springer (2018).

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: To an extent, yes, for the Tamil Vedas: the poets who composed the poems that make up the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham were after all humans by birth, despite being incarnations of divine beings.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The scriptures are not to be tampered with, nor the ideas found in them interpreted as per the will of the individual.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Hagiographic texts as well as commentaries on the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham (12th c. onwards) mention assemblies where specialists debate on the correct interpretation of key topics.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

Notes: It is only educated and acknowledged scholars who have that power.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: As pointed out earlier on, interpreting or revisiting interpretations are the realm of acknowledged scholars, often ācāryas, who are officially sanctioned figures.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on what needs to be transmitted, it is the ācārya who transmits esoteric scriptures. As for the Divya Prabandham, anyone who can recite it can transmit to the others.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: We can mention here both the Vedas and the Divya Prabandham. The recitation of both scriptures are codified, both at home and in public places such as the temple.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: NB: Further research is required in the field. Temples are built according to rules of architecture prescribed for a larger community of Vedic believers, with specialized rules and rituals for the Śrīvaiṣṇava ones, but it is not clear if this group itself built temples. Maṭhas (roughly, monasteries), resting places for Vaiṣṇava travellers (Rāmānucakūṭams) are also built, although they cannot be called "monumental." Deceased ācāryas have their mortal remains buried and a small structure (known as a tiruvaracu or br̥ndāvanam) with a shrine built upon. The place is worshipped by the disciples and other Śrīvaiṣṇavas.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Please see previous answer.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Iconography is well developed, as God in His iconic form is very important for the worship of humans. Arcā (or "image") is one of God's five forms, and ācāryas like Piḷḷai Lokācārya believe that once an icon is made, it is verily God's body, not to be thought in terms of the material it was made of.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

Notes: Homes have altars for private worship; temples are public places where elaborate worship of the image of God and His people is made.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Icons of Nārāyaṇa and His entourage are represented like full-fledged human beings (but not just), with added divine features, like extra arms. Eyes are an important feature on the face of the Deity.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is worshipped in His half-lion, half-man form (Narasimha), in His boar and other such forms. His vehicle, Garuḍa the eagle, is also worshipped in the temples.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Most natural elements (like mountain, rain, etc.) have a deity as their spirit, and this is not specific to Śrīvaiṣṇava belief, which simply claims that they all have Nārāyaṇa as their Master.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is represented as having a human form (except when He appears as an animal), plus distinguishing features like a pair of extra arms. The same goes for His entourage (i.e. His wives, servants, etc.).

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: God is all-pervasive, so all places and things can be a reference to Him. Like the number 26.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Many Śrīvaiṣṇava texts, including Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Arcirādi, describe in detail afterlife, i.e. the soul's progress towards Vaikuṅṭha, and also what life is like there. Iconographic representations of this exist now, but it is not clear if they were represented during that period of time.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: One example is the pair of Nārāyaṇa's weapons, the conch and the discus, branded on the devotees upper arms during initiation. There is also the vertical marks made on the forehead (among other places), which represent the feet of Nārāyaṇa.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: The Lord's human devotees are also represented and worshipped, probably already by Rāmānuja's time. He himself had two of his statues made during his lifetime, according to hagiographic texts such as the Guruparamparāprabhāvam.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: There are many features, like Nārāyaṇa is represented as seated, standing or reclining. For more information on this topic, please see Champakalakshmi, R. (1981). Vaiṣṇava iconography in the Tamil country. New Delhi: Orient Longman.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Temples are sacred places of public worship; homes also have an altar, which is also sacred. Of special importance are the temples/temple-towns praised by the Āḷvārs in their poetry (those places are known as divyadeśams, or "divine places"), but also places with mythological links, like Dvāraka and Ayodhyā, (allegedly) Kṛṣṇa's and Rāma's birthplaces respectively.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Often the temple is situated by a river, on a hill, or by the ocean. For example, Śrīraṅgam, the most important Śrīvaiṣṇava temple already by Rāmānuja's time, is praised as much as the river Kāveri that surrounds it. Vēṅkaṭam, currently known as Tirumalā-Tirupati, has been another important temple for centuries, and it was built on a hill, which is much praised and revered both by the Āḷvārs and by the ācāryas.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam and other hagiographic texts mention pilgrimage, and sometimes how people come upon interesting events while on a pilgrimage, e.g. Nāthamuni getting a message to come back and settle in Southern India, or Rāmānuja going as far away as to modern-day Jammu.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: Pilgrimage is important but not necessarily obligatory. The ascetics are supposed not to stay put in one place for more than a few weeks, except during the monsoon, but lay devotees, although encouraged to visit sacred places, are not censured for not doing so.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: There definitely is a distinction between spirit and body. According to Śrīvaiṣṇavism, the worst illusion in humans consists in confusing the body to be the same as the spirit. The spirit is eternal, and can get into another body according to its karma, whereas that particular body disintegrates. The spirit-body concept takes a whole new dimension as Śrīvaiṣṇavism sees everything other than God (i.e. other sentient and insentient beings) as being God's body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit is said to be eternal and sentient, whereas the body is constantly changing and insentient. The soul also has had an endless number of births, hence countless numbers of bodies.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Most definitely. The spirit is sentient and non-material, whereas the body is insentient and material.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: This relationship is taken to another level, when everything in this world, including the spirits of all the sentient beings as well as insentient beings, are considered as the body of God.

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Every action that a human performs, every thought and word have multiple witnesses, including the sun and the moon, let alone God who resides in him/her. Any good behaviour (i.e., behaving according to the prescriptions of the scriptures) and every bad behaviour (behaving in contradiction to the scriptures) are recorded and they lead to karma, good and bad respectively.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Taboos concerning food are many, as food intake is more than for the sake of subsistence.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Respect of sacred objects are a must.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: They care about humans applying divine laws of conduct, whatever field they may pertain to.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of any living being outside the allowed domain is monitored and punished. That of a coreligionist entails worse punishment.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Any unwarranted crime is condemned, as every soul is said to be God's body.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: See previous answer.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Sex should remain within the bounds of what is acceptable (i.e. what is approved of by scriptures such as Manu-dharma). Sexual practices are also monitored, and lead to bad karma when they happen without the approved boundaries.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: More often than not, it is a bigger sin if the adulterer is a woman. But extramarital physical relations are condemned in general for people desiring piety.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is a big no-no.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Speaking the truth is one of the fundamental requirements of "Hindusim," and this goes beyond the limits of this particular faith.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: This is linked with speaking the truth.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Performing black magic for the sake of harming someone else is frowned upon.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Undue and unjustified fights are frowned upon.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: God, His qualities and acts and His devotees must make up the bulk of any conversation. Malignant gossip is especially to be frowned upon, particularly if it has for its object another Śrīvaiṣṇava, and it leads to bad karma.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Fairness is important whatever the field.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: As mentioned in ones of the notes, every thought, word and deed of a human is monitored. And each is supposed tin accordance with scriptures.

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This religious groups agrees with some texts that are common to other Vedic groups too, e.g. scriptures such as Manu's dharma code.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This school does believe in the coming of God as Kalki, who is supposed to establish order and justice in this world at the end of Kaliyuga, but there is rarely any emphasis or even mention of this. What is essential for a human being is to behave properly in this birth so that the soul can achieve liberation at death.

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The whole panoply of supernatural beings, both good and bad, found in the Hindu epics and

purāṇas equally belong to the Śrīvaiṣṇa system, although there is only one Supreme Being, Nārāyaṇa.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

— Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is the Supreme Being, and everyone and everything else is subordinate to Him.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

— Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is anthropomorphic, although he has extra-features (like extra arms, and absolute power to do anything) that humans do not have.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

— No

Notes: Although the word "sky" is sometimes used to refer to Nārāyaṇa's abode, he is not merely a sky deity: He is the all-pervading Supreme Being, who is the Master of all.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

— No

Notes: Nārāyaṇa does not pertain to the underworld, but as pointed out earlier, being omnipresent, even that part of the world is not devoid of His presence.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

— No

Notes: Yes and no. Some Hindu texts believe that the king is an aṃśa ("fragment") of Viṣṇu. But in Śrīvaiṣṇavism, the king is not high god.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

— Yes

Notes: As pointed out in my previous answer, some Hindu texts do claim that the king is a manifestation of god on earth, but the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas of the default period have rather worshipped Nārāyaṇa Himself, or their own teachers, rather than treat a king as a representative of God.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

— No

Notes: The Supreme Being is a kin relation to each and every soul, not just the elite. Medieval Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas, like the commentator Periyavāccāṅ Piḷḷai, use the expression "nirupādhika-bandhu" (kin without conditions) to refer to God, as His relation with the souls is natural and unconditional, as opposed to relations between humans, which depend on birth, etc.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

— No

Notes: All connections one can have with the Supreme Being does not depend on being part of the elite.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

— Yes

Notes: Absolutely, even though He has to punish the bad. His goodness, although inherent, is enhanced by His affection for the souls, which is compared to the affection that the cow feels for its calf (vātsalya). This allows Him to overlook the flaws in His devotees.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

— Yes [specify]: His features are many, but if we focus on the good qualities that He is said to have, we get an impressive list. Śrīvaiṣṇava texts, such as Rāmānuja's own works, refer to many of these. John Carman (in *The Theology of Rāmānuja. An Essay in Interreligious Understanding*. New Haven & London: Yale University Press, 1974: 79-80) thus enumerates the following qualities, as per Rāmānuja's commentary on the Bhagavad-Gītā: 1) the six attributes of Bhagavān ('God'): jñāna ('knowledge'), bala ('strength'), aiśvarya ('sovereignty'), vīrya ('immutability'), śakti ('[creative] power') and tejas ('splendour'); 2) qualities linked with compassion: sauśīlya ('gracious condescension'), vātsalya ('tenderness' like that of a cow for its calf), but also sauhārda ('friendliness'), anurāga ('passionate affection') and saundarya ('beauty'). Suzanne Siauve (*Aṣṭādaśabhedanirṇaya. Aṣṭādaśabhedanirṇaya. Explication des dix-huits différences (entre les deux branches de l'École de Rāmānuja) de Vātsya Raṅganāṭha*. Critically edited, translated & annotated by Suzanne Siauve. Pondichéry: Institut Français d'Indologie, 1978: 27fn5) adds a few extra ones, based on Vedānta Deśika's commentary on Rāmānuja's Śaraṅāgati-gadyam: mārḍava ('pliancy'), ārjava ('honesty'), sāmya ('equity'), kāruṇya ('compassion'), mādhyura ('sweetness'), gāmbhīrya ('depth'), audārya ('generosity'), cāturya ('deftness'), sthairyā ('firmness'), dhairyā ('courage'), śaurya ('valour'), parākrama ('heroism'), satyakāma ('He whose desires are realised'), satyasaṅkalpa ('firmness of resolve'), kṛtīva ('possession of all actions') and kṛtajñatā ('gratitude').

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

— Yes

Notes: The Supreme Being, Nārāyaṇa, is omniscient, and is claimed to know everything that is there to know, in past, present and future.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

— No

Notes: The Supreme God knows absolutely everything, and is definitely not limited to the domain of human affairs. In fact, it is claimed that the only thing He does not know is the extent of His own greatness, to which it is sometimes pointed out, that even God can only know what exists, i.e. there is no limit to His

greatness, so He cannot know about it.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The Supreme God is omniscient. Please see my answer to the first sub-question.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: It is unrestricted anywhere in the world, not just in the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: He is omniscient and omnipotent. His knowledge is unrestricted anywhere in the world, whatever the region.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The whole world and all the souls being His body, and He being the antarātmā (the inner controller) of everyone, Nārāyaṇa can see you from everywhere, outside, inside, anytime.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, He sees absolutely everything at all times, whatever the circumstance.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: As pointed out earlier, He is the inner controller (antarātmā) in everyone, so he sees and understands everything that happens in one's mind, including hidden motives.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, and a lot more than that: He knows the basic character not just in this birth, but in all the births that a soul has had.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: It is claimed that the Supreme Being knows the happenings of all three times (trikāla: past, present, and future), so He knows what will happen to you in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He knows what humans cannot perceive. He knows everything there is to know about this and other worlds.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: This belief is not exclusive to Śrīvaiṣṇavism. A rewarding God is to be seen in many Hindu belief systems.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme Being can punish (which roughly corresponds to a soul's bad karma), although He is more tolerant of the mistakes of His devotees who have taken refuge in Him.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Given that He is omniscient and everything that happens in this world also depend on Him (but equally on a person's karma), there are very few things that escape His notice or will.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, for example, when a devotee does something good, this causes the Supreme Being to be happy. So many of the ācāryas suggest that whatever we do, we should do it for the sake of His mukhollāsa ("the joy in the face").

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Although imperturbable, the Supreme being can get angry for example (e.g. when a Śrīvaiṣṇava devotee is ill-treated). However, there will be more debates about among

Śrīvaiṣṇavas already by the end of the sample period. After this period, there will be a division between the school that believes that God feels so much empathy that He feels the pain of the devotee, and the other that believes that although God has sympathy, He does not have such feelings. For more on this topic, please see *Aṣṭādaśabhedanirṇaya*. *Explication des dix-huits différences (entre les deux branches de l'École de Rāmānuja) de Vātsya Raṅganāṭha*. Critically edited, translated & annotated by Suzanne Siauve. Pondichéry: Institut Français d'Indologie, 1978.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: The Supreme Being does not have bodily needs.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Yes and no: strictly speaking, there is but one Supreme God, who alone should be worshipped, worshipping other gods, like Śiva, is a complete no-no. At the same time, Nārāyaṇa's "family" and devotees can be/should be worshipped, and this includes His wife Śrī, as well as His devotees-both human and supernatural-like the Āḷvārs and the divyasūris (eternally free souls).

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: I have listed many of His features in an answer above. It is worth mentioning that the Supreme Being is the sole one capable of granting moksha/liberation for a soul.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The hagiographic text, *Guruparamparāprabhāvam*, mentions that although God is supposed to maintain a silence that is due to His arcā (image) form, He communicated with a select set of people. One of them is Tirukkacci Nampi, who spoke to Varadarāja, the name of Nārāyaṇa in the main Vaiṣṇava temple in Kāñcīpuram, as he fanned His image. The *Guruparamparāprabhāvam* narrates how Rāmānuja asked Nampi to help him with a few doubts that he had, and Nampi had the Lord clear those doubts through his (Nampi's) mediation. This is but one example found in the *Guruparamparāprabhāvam*.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: On many occasions, the *Guruparamparāprabhāvam* tells the story of how someone had a dream in which God communicated with him/her. For example, when Rāmānuja runs out of white clay with which he used to make his religious

marks on his forehead and the rest of his body, the Lord appeared in his dream to tell him where to find some.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam mentions how sometimes communicates through his priests (arcakamukhena), which is most probably a reference to a person who is in trance.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: It is more in the sense of instinct or insight.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: The king does not have any such role.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: God is sometimes said to appear directly in front of the devotee. For example, the Guruparamparāprabhāvam describes how the icon of Nārāyaṇa moved and came to Rāmānuja and sat on his lap, when the saint went to recover it from a Delhi sultan.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits, turned into other supernatural beings, can sometimes possess a person; or can be reborn into a human, or anything else. But other than that, there isn't profuse mention of such spirits.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: We can cite the example of a brahmarākṣasa ("a kind of evil demon, the ghost of a Brāhman who led an unholy life" Monier-Williams), who is seen interacting with Nampāṭuvāṇ, a devotee of Nārāyaṇa. It is a favourite story with the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: As pointed out earlier, some such creatures can possess one's body, e.g. the daughter of the Jain king, whom Rāmānuja is said to have cured (Guruparamparāprabhāvam). In that way, their presence can be felt.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Not being God, their knowledge is much limited.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Such spirits do not have the kind of knowledge that God has.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The previously human spirit's knowledge is limited in terms of content, and possibly also geographically.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: E.g.: In the case of the devotee Nampāṭuvāṇ, the hagiographic texts mention how the brahmarākṣasa spotted him travelling and decided to eat him.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: To take the same example once again, Nampāṭuvāṇ was spotted by the spirit at night.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not very clear. In Nampāṭuvāṇ's story, the spirit does not seem to know his heart, and therefore initially refuses to believe his promise to come back to it after worshipping the Lord in the temple (when he had the intention to do so,

according to the story).

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: It would seem so, although I'm yet to come across stories that elaborate more on this topic.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: They have some future sight in some cases, but are in no way omniscient. Some ascetics (although not merely spirits) are said to possess future sight.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: If at all, it is very limited. It is God and His people (acting under His permission) who have such efficacy (though it is mostly God).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Please refer to Nampāṭuvāṇ's story, in which the brahmarākṣasa (the spirit) seeks to eat him, being very hungry.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They seem in general to be malevolent.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: We can refer to Nampāṭuvāṇ's story once again, The spirit in question decides to eat this man, who then enters upon a negotiation with the spirit.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: The king is not involved in this any more than the average human.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: We can take the example of the nityasūris, or the eternally free souls on the one hand, and that of other gods (e.g. Indra, Śiva, etc.). The former are non-human servants of Nārāyaṇa, who serve Him in Vaikuṇṭha, and they possess supernatural powers that humans do not and are comparable to God in many ways. The latter possess more power and knowledge than the humans, but are by no means as knowledgeable or powerful as God, being themselves baddhātmās ("bound souls").

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: These can be seen if they take a human form to interact. The life-story of Vedānta Deśika narrates how Garuḍa, Nārāyaṇa's avian vehicle, appeared in his presence after Deśika intensely worshipped him. The Guruparamparāprabhāvam (chapter "Tirumaḷicai Āḷvār vaibhavam") describes the encounter between Śiva and Tirumaḷicai Ālvār.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible, if they choose to make themselves felt.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The nityasūris' knowledge is almost as perfect as God's. But the other supernatural beings like Brahmā or Śiva have a limited/defective knowledge.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: If it's nityasūris, they are near omniscient. But other non human beings like other gods like Śiva know more than the average human does, but they are by no means omniscient.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: For the same reasons mentioned above. Both nityasūris and other supernatural beings have a knowledge that is not necessarily restricted to a specific area of the sample region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Please see previous answers for more information.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on who the supernatural being, this is possible.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible

(in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Again, it depends on the supernatural being.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Causal efficacy is the domain of God, anything the other beings do is subject to His will and approval.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As point out earlier, if at all, causal efficacy in non-human supernatural beings depends on God.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam (chapter "Tirumaḷicai Āḷvār vaibhavam") describes how when Śiva, a non human supernatural being, was not given respect by an Āḷvār (Tirumaḷicai), he became angry and started to attack him.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Stories of how a hungry Indra attacked the people of Bṛndāvana for worshipping and feeding the Govardhana mountain instead, etc. abound not just in the hagiography, but also in other forms of writing, like commentaries on the Divya Prabandham. Garuḍa, himself a nityasūri (an eternally free soul), got angry against God for granting refuge to a snake that he wanted to eat, because he was so hungry.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: We can take the Āḷvārs to fit in this category. Being eternally free souls (who are non-human), they were born as humans in this world. Hagiography describes them as having both human and divine experiences.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: If we take the āḷvārs for example, divine beings born as humans-hence mixed human-divine beings who can sometimes pull off miracles-then, yes, they can be seen.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: If they are semi-human, then yes.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: They tend to know a bit more than that due to their unclouded knowledge.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific

area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: It is not always clear how much they know. There is no fixed rule as to how (un)restricted their knowledge is.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no, in the sense that not being God, they do not necessarily know everything there is to know. But at the same time, their knowledge is not necessarily restricted within a region. But there is no fixed rule as to how (un)restricted their knowledge is.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Having a clearer mind and knowledge, they may sometimes realize what may happen, but it is not clear whether there is future sight. The Guruparamparāprabhāvam (chapter "Mutālāṅvār vaibhavam"), for example, describes how the first three Āṅvārs found themselves in the same place (where they were later joined by god Himself), but had no idea who the other was.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: If we take the Āḷvārs, their emotions are often linked to their experience with God. if they feel united with Him, they express joy, otherwise no.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: When going through human experience, they sometimes feel emotions such as sadness, anger, etc. Hagiography narrates how Periyāḷvār was sad at having married off his daughter to God Himself, and how Tirumaṅkai Āḷvār became angry at not being able to visit a temple immediately after his visit to a certain town.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Such things are not always mentioned. One important exception is Nammāḷvār, who is said not to have felt hunger or thirst from the moment he was born, and sat without any kind of nourishment for years.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes
Notes: The Āḷvārs interacted with humans, living among them.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam narrates how Nammālvār communicated with Nāthamuni, much time after he passed away. The text seems to imply that Nāthamuni, who sat reciting verses by Nammālvār's disciple Madhurakavi, was able to see the poet and speak to him directly. This could be a way of saying that he was in a trance when he got the visit.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa ranks highest along with His consort Śrī, followed by the nityasūris.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: If we take gods such as Indra and Varuṇa as nonhuman supernatural beings, then their power is domain-specific. However, as unborn, true devotees of God, the nityasūris have a wider scope of power.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: For the initiated, it is a spatial location, Nārāyaṇa's abode, known as Vaikuṅṭha. For all the others, rebirths and stays in other places, such as heaven or hell [which are both non-permanent], are the alternatives.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The spatial location of the afterlife, especially for the initiated, is very much mentioned and described in the Śrīvaiṣṇava literature: it is Vaikuṅṭha, and even the path that takes the soul from the dead body to this abode is described in detail in works such as Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Arcirādi. As for the uninitiated, there are other (non-permanent) places to go to after death: if it's not rebirth into a different body, then it could be a stay in heaven or hell, for example. The belief is that no place is permanent except Vaikuṅṭha. Hell, heaven and other non-terrestrial places are widely described in various purāṇas.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as mentioned in my previous answers, it is known as Vaikuṅṭha.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Notes: Although sometimes referred to as the place above (as Vaikuṅṭha is believed to be above this world), it is never meant to be a vague definition.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: It depends what "other" is. As I have mentioned earlier on, afterlife for the initiated is in Vaikuṅṭha. There are two worlds: one is this one material world, known as līlāvibhūti, or the world of sport [for God], and the other is nityavibhūti, or the eternal place, which corresponds to Vaikuṅṭha. So, seen from that perspective, yes, afterlife is located in another space.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: They do on behalf of God, like the planets that affect people's lives.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

Notes: The average human being cannot know all this, although, the fact that God is behind the meting out of justice is not hidden from anyone.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Notes: The reason is not known, especially if one suffers due to the karma acquired in a different birth. Usually sufferings are a result of bad karma, and with the help of astrologers or enlightened people, it is possible to know the cause for one's suffering (bad behaviour, transgression of the religious laws, etc.).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is a means of preventing what is perceived as wayward behaviour and to encourage people to become Śrīvaiṣṇavas, which will end once for all their karma and give them liberation.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: Yes and no. The punishment is proportional to the offence. It could be mild, but it could also be very terrible.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: See previous note.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: This is definitely a possibility. It is said that those who have sinned in their thoughts are born as lower ranking humans, those who have sinned through their words are reborn as animals, and those who have sinned with their bodies are born as trees, etc. But those who have sought refuge at Rāmānuja's feet by becoming Śrīvaiṣṇavas will be spared such a fate, as liberation is guaranteed to them at the end of the bodies.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is a possibility, although I'm yet to come across an example that illustrates this.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The Garuḍa Purāṇa, which is an authoritative text, is made up of lists of punishments that are meted out for the various crimes that are committed. And the punishments are as numerous as the crimes/sins that can be committed.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Punishments in general are emphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.
- ↳ Other [specify]
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Reincarnation is definitely a possibility, although it is not a concept restricted to Śrīvaiṣṇavism (as other hindus, Jains and Buddhists also believe in this). Besides which, this faith system promises the end of the cycle of birth and death (hence of reincarnation) for the soul of the one who has taken refuge in God.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: It can be a human form, or an animal, or even an insentient being, depending on how good or bad one's karma is. Good karma means better birth, i.e. as a human, bad karma means lower birth (e.g. as plants). It is said that those who sin with their thoughts are born as lower class/caste humans, those who have sinned through their words are reborn as animals and those who have sinned with their bodies are reborn as insentient beings.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Please see previous answers.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Please see previous answers. This is also possible. It depends on how good or bad one's karma is. Very bad karma can lead one to be born as an inanimate/insentient object.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Most definitely yes. Please see my answers to previous questions. Karma is as eternal as the soul, and disappears only when the soul reaches Vaikuṅṭha. So till the soul stays out of Vaikuṅṭha, karma keeps dealing with it.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

–Yes [specify]: Although once a soul achieves liberation and reaches Vaikuṅṭha it does not come back to this world, sometimes, some great souls, especially nityasūris (who were never bound by karma), choose to incarnate themselves to further God's cause and/or salvage humans. E.g. Rāmānuja, who is claimed to be an incarnation of the serpent Ananta, upon whom Narayana sleeps in Vaikuṅṭha.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Notes: The cause can mostly be known by seeking out help of astrologers and/or enlightened people.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The best reward is the liberation of the soul, which reaches God's abode, Vaikuṅṭha. This is invariably emphasized.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the Śrīvaiṣṇavas are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the Śrīvaiṣṇavas are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, who are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God, thereby liberating their souls from the cycle of birth and death.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the Śrīvaiṣṇavas are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the Śrīvaiṣṇavas are supposed to reach the

heavenly abode of God.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Karma, whether good or bad, obstructs the path to liberation. So rewards other than proximity and service to god and His devotees are not emphasized.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving

God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
— Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
— Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
— Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
— Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
— Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
— Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Other [specify]
— Yes

Notes: Many are the rewards that people get in this life for good behaviour. But again, this is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Lay Śrīvaiṣṇavas are usually cremated according to the general "Hindu" prescriptions, to which are added some Śrīvaiṣṇava rites and chanting. Please check <http://www.srimatham.com/death-samskara.html> for further information.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: The one famous exception that I know of is Rāmānuja's body, which has been preserved for centuries. It is believed that inside the shrine dedicated to him in Śrīraṅgam, we can still see his preserved body.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Burial is done especially for the ācāryas, and a small structure, called bṛndāvanam or tiruvaracu, is built upon it. It usually hosts a shrine. It is not clear if the same practice existed in the default period.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: It is not clear what the practices were. In the modern context, the ācāryas are buried in a seated position, and therefore, their legs are bent. Please see the photo and video of a modern-day burial of an ācārya on this webpage: <http://anudinam.org/2013/05/19/hh-45th-azhagiyasingar-attains-acharyan-thiruvadi/>

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: This is for the lay people.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Religious heads, ācāryas and other such people, are interred in a seated position (cross-legged).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: This is completely non-existent.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: There is no such practice among the Śrīvaiṣṇavas.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: The initiated who are buried are usually (though not always) religious heads. The location is individually picked.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: For the same reason mentioned above, and because cemetery as a concept is not as common as the cremation ground, family tomb crypts do not exist.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: Some religious heads can be buried at a place where they lived, but in general not under a house. Besides, the place they are buried is marked, and worshipped by later generations.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Religious leaders (ācāryas and others) have a shrine built upon where they are buried.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Everything is cyclical in this belief system, good follows bad and vice versa. A new, better world will rise after this one that endures the hardships of kaliyuga, but that good world will be destroyed in order to let a bad world come into existence, and so on and so forth.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: For the warrior caste (kṣatriyas), yes.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: Cowardice is a sign of tāmasa ("darkness") quality, hence to be avoided.

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: These are qualities that are important in for example the kings. Not a necessary virtue for Śrīvaiṣṇavas. Although nobility of character is a more universal requirement.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: emphasis is on inner beauty, not on the external one, which can make things by making one vain.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: There definitely is a distinction between spirit and body. According to Śrīvaiṣṇavism, the worst illusion in humans consists in confusing the body to be the same as the spirit. The spirit is eternal, and can get into another body according to its karma, whereas that particular body disintegrates. The spirit-body concept takes a whole new dimension as Śrīvaiṣṇavism sees everything other than God (i.e. other sentient and insentient beings) as being God's body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit is said to be eternal and sentient, whereas the body is constantly changing and insentient. The soul also has had an endless number of births, hence countless numbers of bodies.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Most definitely. The spirit is sentient and non-material, whereas the body is insentient

and material.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: This relationship is taken to another level, when everything in this world, including the spirits of all the sentient beings as well as insentient beings, are considered as the body of God.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: For the initiated, it is a spatial location, Nārāyaṇa's abode, known as Vaikuṅṭha. For all the others, rebirths and stays in other places, such as heaven or hell [which are both non-permanent], are the alternatives.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The spatial location of the afterlife, especially for the initiated, is very much mentioned and described in the Śrīvaiṣṇava literature: it is Vaikuṅṭha, and even the path that takes the soul from the dead body to this abode is described in detail in works such as Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Arcirādi. As for the uninitiated, there are other (non-permanent) places to go to after death: if it's not rebirth into a different body, then it could be a stay in heaven or hell, for example. The belief is that no place is permanent except Vaikuṅṭha. Hell, heaven and other non-terrestrial places are widely described in various purāṇas.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as mentioned in my previous answers, it is known as Vaikuṅṭha.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Notes: Although sometimes referred to as the place above (as Vaikuṅṭha is believed to be above this world), it is never meant to be a vague definition.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: It depends what "other" is. As I have mentioned earlier on, afterlife for the

initiated is in *Vaikuṅṭha*. There are two worlds: one is this one material world, known as *līlāvibhūti*, or the world of sport [for God], and the other is *nityavibhūti*, or the eternal place, which corresponds to *Vaikuṅṭha*. So, seen from that perspective, yes, afterlife is located in another space.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Reincarnation is definitely a possibility, although it is not a concept restricted to Śrīvaiṣṇavism (as other hindus, Jains and Buddhists also believe in this). Besides which, this faith system promises the end of the cycle of birth and death (hence of reincarnation) for the soul of the one who has taken refuge in God.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: It can be a human form, or an animal, or even an insentient being, depending on how good or bad one's karma is. Good karma means better birth, i.e. as a human, bad karma means lower birth (e.g. as plants). It is said that those who sin with their thoughts are born as lower class/caste humans, those who have sinned through their words are reborn as animals and those who have sinned with their bodies are reborn as insentient beings.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Please see previous answers.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Please see previous answers. This is also possible. It depends on how good or bad one's karma is. Very bad karma can lead one to be born as an inanimate/insentient object.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Most definitely yes. Please see my answers to previous questions. Karma is as eternal as the soul, and disappears only when the soul reaches *Vaikuṅṭha*. So till the soul stays out of *Vaikuṅṭha*, karma keeps dealing with it.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: Although once a soul achieves liberation and reaches *Vaikuṅṭha* it does not come back to this world, sometimes, some great souls, especially *nityasūris* (who were never bound

by karma), choose to incarnate themselves to further God's cause and/or salvage humans. E.g. Rāmānuja, who is claimed to be an incarnation of the serpent Ananta, upon whom Narayana sleeps in Vaikuṅṭha.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Lay Śrīvaiṣṇavas are usually cremated according to the general "Hindu" prescriptions, to which are added some Śrīvaiṣṇava rites and chanting. Please check <http://www.srimatham.com/death-samskara.html> for further information.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: The one famous exception that I know of is Rāmānuja's body, which has been preserved for centuries. It is believed that inside the shrine dedicated to him in Śrīraṅgam, we can still see his preserved body.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Burial is done especially for the ācāryas, and a small structure, called bṛndāvanam or tiruvaracu, is built upon it. It usually hosts a shrine. It is not clear if the same practice existed in the default period.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: It is not clear what the practices were. In the modern context, the ācāryas are buried in a seated position, and therefore, their legs are bent. Please see the photo and video of a modern-day burial of an ācārya on this webpage: <http://anudinam.org/2013/05/19/hh-45th-azhagiyasingar-attains-acharyan-thiruvadi/>

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: This is for the lay people.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

–Yes [specify]: Religious heads, ācāryas and other such people, are interred in a seated position (cross-legged).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: This is completely non-existent.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: There is no such practice among the Śrīvaiṣṇavas.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: The initiated who are buried are usually (though not always) religious heads. The location is individually picked.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: For the same reason mentioned above, and because cemetery as a concept is not as common as the cremation ground, family tomb crypts do not exist.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: Some religious heads can be buried at a place where they lived, but in general not under a house. Besides, the place they are buried is marked, and worshipped by later generations.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Religious leaders (ācāryas and others) have a shrine built upon where they are buried.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The whole panoply of supernatural beings, both good and bad, found in the Hindu epics and purāṇas equally belong to the Śrīvaiṣṇa system, although there is only one Supreme Being, Nārāyaṇa.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is the Supreme Being, and everyone and everything else is subordinate to Him.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa is anthropomorphic, although he has extra-features (like extra arms, and absolute power to do anything) that humans do not have.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: Although the word "sky" is sometimes used to refer to Nārāyaṇa's abode, he is not merely a sky deity: He is the all-pervading Supreme Being, who is the Master of all.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Nārāyaṇa does not pertain to the underworld, but as pointed out earlier, being omnipresent, even that part of the world is not devoid of His presence.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Yes and no. Some Hindu texts believe that the king is an aṃśa ("fragment") of Viṣṇu. But in Śrīvaiṣṇavism, the king is not high god.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: As pointed out in my previous answer, some Hindu texts do claim that the king is a manifestation of god on earth, but the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas of the default period have rather worshipped Nārāyaṇa Himself, or their own teachers, rather than treat a king as a representative of God.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The Supreme Being is a kin relation to each and every soul, not just the elite. Medieval Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas, like the commentator Periyavāccāṅ Piḷḷai, use the expression "nirupādhika-bandhu" (kin without conditions) to refer to God, as His relation with the souls is natural and unconditional, as opposed to relations between humans, which depend on birth, etc.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: All connections one can have with the Supreme Being does not depend on being part of the elite.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Absolutely, even though He has to punish the bad. His goodness, although inherent, is enhanced by His affection for the souls, which is compared to the affection that the cow feels for its calf (vātsalya). This allows Him to overlook the flaws in His devotees.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: His features are many, but if we focus on the good qualities that He is said to have, we get an impressive list. Śrīvaiṣṇava texts, such as Rāmānuja's own works, refer to many of these. John Carman (in *The Theology of Rāmānuja. An Essay in Interreligious Understanding*. New Haven & London: Yale University Press, 1974: 79-80)

thus enumerates the following qualities, as per Rāmānuja's commentary on the Bhagavad-Gītā: 1) the six attributes of Bhagavān ('God'): jñāna ('knowledge'), bala ('strength'), aiśvarya ('sovereignty'), vīrya ('immutability'), śakti ('[creative] power') and tejas ('splendour'); 2) qualities linked with compassion: sauśīlya ('gracious condescension'), vātsalya ('tenderness' like that of a cow for its calf), but also sauhārda ('friendliness'), anurāga ('passionate affection') and saundarya ('beauty'). Suzanne Siauve (Aṣṭādaśabhedanirṇaya. Aṣṭādaśabhedanirṇaya. Explication des dix-huits différences (entre les deux branches de l'École de Rāmānuja) de Vātsya Raṅganāṭha. Critically edited, translated & annotated by Suzanne Siauve. Pondichéry: Institut Français d'Indologie, 1978: 27fn5) adds a few extra ones, based on Vedānta Deśika's commentary on Rāmānuja's Śaraṅgati-gadyam: mārḍava ('pliancy'), ārjava ('honesty'), sāmya ('equity'), kāruṇya ('compassion'), mādhyura ('sweetness'), gāmbhīrya ('depth'), audārya ('generosity'), cāturya ('deftness'), sthairyā ('firmness'), dhairyā ('courage'), śaurya ('valour'), parākrama ('heroism'), satyakāma ('He whose desires are realised'), satyasaṅkalpa ('firmness of resolve'), kṛtīva ('possession of all actions') and kṛtajñatā ('gratitude').

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme Being, Nārāyaṇa, is omniscient, and is claimed to know everything that is there to know, in past, present and future.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The Supreme God knows absolutely everything, and is definitely not limited to the domain of human affairs. In fact, it is claimed that the only thing He does not know is the extent of His own greatness, to which it is sometimes pointed out, that even God can only know what exists, i.e. there is no limit to His greatness, so He cannot know about it.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The Supreme God is omniscient. Please see my answer to the first sub-question.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: It is unrestricted anywhere in the world, not just in the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: He is omniscient and omnipotent. His knowledge is unrestricted anywhere in the world, whatever the region.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The whole world and all the souls being His body, and He being the antarātmā (the inner controller) of everyone, Nārāyaṇa can see you from everywhere, outside, inside, anytime.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, He sees absolutely everything at all times, whatever the circumstance.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: As pointed out earlier, He is the inner controller (antarātmā) in everyone, so he sees and understands everything that happens in one's mind, including hidden motives.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, and a lot more than that: He knows the basic character not just in this birth, but in all the births that a soul has had.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: It is claimed that the Supreme Being knows the happenings of all three times (trikāla: past, present, and future), so He knows what will happen to you in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He knows what humans cannot perceive. He knows everything there is to know about this and other worlds.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: This belief is not exclusive to Śrīvaiṣṇavism. A rewarding God is to be seen in many Hindu belief systems.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme Being can punish (which roughly corresponds to a soul's bad karma), although He is more tolerant of the mistakes of His devotees who have taken refuge in Him.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Given that He is omniscient and everything that happens in this world also depend on Him (but equally on a person's karma), there are very few things that escape His notice or will.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, for example, when a devotee does something good, this causes the Supreme Being to be happy. So many of the ācāryas suggest that whatever we do, we should do it for the sake of His mukhollāsa ("the joy in the face").

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Although imperturbable, the Supreme being can get angry for example (e.g. when a Śrīvaiṣṇava devotee is ill-treated). However, there will be more debates about among Śrīvaiṣṇavas already by the end of the sample period. After this period, there will be a division between the school that believes that God feels so much empathy that He feels the pain of the devotee, and the other that believes that although God has sympathy, He does not have such feelings. For more on this topic, please see *Aṣṭādaśabhedanirṇaya. Explication des dix-huits différences (entre les deux branches de l'École de Rāmānuja) de Vātsya Raṅganāṭha. Critically edited, translated & annotated by Suzanne Siauve. Pondichéry: Institut Français d'Indologie, 1978.*

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: The Supreme Being does not have bodily needs.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Yes and no: strictly speaking, there is but one Supreme God, who alone should

be worshipped, worshipping other gods, like Śiva, is a complete no-no. At the same time, Nārāyaṇa's "family" and devotees can be/should be worshipped, and this includes His wife Śrī, as well as His devotees-both human and supernatural-like the Āḷvārs and the divyasūris (eternally free souls).

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: I have listed many of His features in an answer above. It is worth mentioning that the Supreme Being is the sole one capable of granting moksha/liberation for a soul.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The hagiographic text, Guruparamparāprabhāvam, mentions that although God is supposed to maintain a silence that is due to His arcā (image) form, He communicated with a select set of people. One of them is Tirukkacci Nampī, who spoke to Varadarāja, the name of Nārāyaṇa in the main Vaiṣṇava temple in Kāñcīpuram, as he fanned His image. The Guruparamparāprabhāvam narrates how Rāmānuja asked Nampī to help him with a few doubts that he had, and Nampī had the Lord clear those doubts through his (Nampī's) mediation. This is but one example found in the Guruparamparāprabhāvam.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: On many occasions, the Guruparamparāprabhāvam tells the story of how someone had a dream in which God communicated with him/her. For example, when Rāmānuja runs out of white clay with which he used to make his religious marks on his forehead and the rest of his body, the Lord appeared in his dream to tell him where to find some.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam mentions how sometimes communicates through his priests (arcakamukhena), which is most probably a reference to a person who is in trance.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: It is more in the sense of instinct or insight.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: The king does not have any such role.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: God is sometimes said to appear directly in front of the devotee. For example, the Guruparamparāprabhāvam describes how the icon of Nārāyaṇa moved and came to Rāmānuja and sat on his lap, when the saint went to recover it from a Delhi sultan.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits, turned into other supernatural beings, can sometimes possess a person; or can be reborn into a human, or anything else. But other than that, there isn't profuse mention of such spirits.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: We can cite the example of a brahmarākṣasa ("a kind of evil demon, the ghost of a Brāhman who led an unholy life" Monier-Williams), who is seen interacting with Nampāṭuvāṇ, a devotee of Nārāyaṇa. It is a favourite story with the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: As pointed out earlier, some such creatures can possess one's body, e.g. the daughter of the Jain king, whom Rāmānuja is said to have cured (Guruparamparāprabhāvam). In that way, their presence can be felt.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Not being God, their knowledge is much limited.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Such spirits do not have the kind of knowledge that God has.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— Yes

Notes: The previously human spirit's knowledge is limited in terms of content, and possibly also geographically.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

— No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

— No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Notes: E.g.: In the case of the devotee Nampāṭuvāṇ, the hagiographic texts mention how the brahmarākṣasa spotted him travelling and decided to eat him.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: To take the same example once again, Nampāṭuvāṇ was spotted by the spirit at night.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not very clear. In Nampāṭuvāṇ's story, the spirit does not seem to know his heart, and therefore initially refuses to believe his promise to come back to it after worshipping the Lord in the temple (when he had the intention to do so, according to the story).

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

— Yes

Notes: It would seem so, although I'm yet to come across stories that elaborate more on this topic.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

— Yes

Notes: They have some future sight in some cases, but are in no way omniscient. Some ascetics (although not merely spirits) are said to possess future sight.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– No

Notes: If at all, it is very limited. It is God and His people (acting under His permission) who have such efficacy (though it is mostly God).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
– Yes

Notes: Please refer to Nampāṭuvāṇ's story, in which the brahmarākṣasa (the spirit) seeks to eat him, being very hungry.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: They seem in general to be malevolent.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes

Notes: We can refer to Nampāṭuvāṇ's story once again, The spirit in question decides to eat this man, who then enters upon a negotiation with the spirit.

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination processes:
– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Notes: The king is not involved in this any more than the average human.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: We can take the example of the nityasūris, or the eternally free souls on the one hand, and that of other gods (e.g. Indra, Śiva, etc.). The former are non-human servants of Nārāyaṇa, who serve Him in Vaikuṅṭha, and they possess supernatural powers that humans do not and are comparable to God in many ways. The latter possess more power and knowledge than the humans, but are by no means as knowledgeable or powerful as God, being themselves baddhātṁās ("bound souls").

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: These can be seen if they take a human form to interact. The life-story of Vedānta Deśika narrates how Garuḍa, Nārāyaṇa's avian vehicle, appeared in his presence after Deśika intensely worshipped him. The Guruparamparāprabhāvam (chapter "Tirumaḷicai Āḷvār vaibhavam") describes the encounter between Śiva and Tirumaḷicai Āḷvār.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible, if they choose to make themselves felt.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The nityasūris' knowledge is almost as perfect as God's. But the other supernatural beings like Brahmā or Śiva have a limited/defective knowledge.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: If it's nityasūris, they are near omniscient. But other non human beings like other gods like Śiva know more than the average human does, but they are by no means omniscient.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: For the same reasons mentioned above. Both nityasūris and other supernatural beings have a knowledge that is not necessarily restricted to a specific area of the sample region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Please see previous answers for more information.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on who the supernatural being, this is possible.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Again, it depends on the supernatural being.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Causal efficacy is the domain of God, anything the other beings do is subject to His will and approval.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As pointed out earlier, if at all, causal efficacy in non-human supernatural beings depends on God.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam (chapter "Tirumaḷicai Āḷvār vaibhavam") describes how when Śiva, a non-human supernatural being, was not given respect by an Āḷvār (Tirumaḷicai), he became angry and started to attack him.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Stories of how a hungry Indra attacked the people of Bṛndāvana for worshipping and feeding the Govardhana mountain instead, etc. abound not just in the hagiography, but also in other forms of writing, like commentaries on the Divya Prabandham. Garuḍa, himself a nityasūri (an eternally free soul), got angry against God for granting refuge to a snake that he wanted to eat, because he was so hungry.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: We can take the Āḷvārs to fit in this category. Being eternally free souls (who are non-human), they were born as humans in this world. Hagiography describes them as having both human and divine experiences.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: If we take the āḷvārs for example, divine beings born as humans-hence mixed human-divine beings who can sometimes pull off miracles-then, yes, they can be seen.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: If they are semi-human, then yes.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: They tend to know a bit more than that due to their unclouded knowledge.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: It is not always clear how much they know. There is no fixed rule as to how (un)restricted their knowledge is.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no, in the sense that not being God, they do not necessarily know everything there is to know. But at the same time, their knowledge is not necessarily restricted within a region. But there is no fixed rule as to how (un)restricted their knowledge is.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Having a clearer mind and knowledge, they may sometimes realize what may happen, but it is not clear whether there is future sight. The Guruparamparāprabhāvam (chapter "Mutalālvār vaibhavam"), for example, describes how the first three Ālvārs found themselves in the same place (where they were later joined by god Himself), but had no idea who the other was.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: If we take the Ālvārs, their emotions are often linked to their experience with God. If they feel united with Him, they express joy, otherwise no.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: When going through human experience, they sometimes feel emotions such as sadness, anger, etc. Hagiography narrates how Periyālvār was sad at having married off his daughter to God Himself, and how Tirumaṅkai Ālvār became angry at not being able to visit a temple immediately after his visit to a certain town.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Such things are not always mentioned. One important exception is Nammālvār, who is said not to have felt hunger or thirst from the moment he was born, and sat without any kind of nourishment for years.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The Ālvārs interacted with humans, living among them.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The Guruparamparāprabhāvam narrates how Nammālvār communicated with Nāthamuni, much time after he passed away. The text seems to imply that Nāthamuni, who sat reciting verses by Nammālvār's disciple Madhurakavi, was able to see the poet and speak to him directly. This could be a way of saying that he was in a trance when he got the visit.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Nārāyaṇa ranks highest along with His consort Śrī, followed by the nityasūris.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: If we take gods such as Indra and Varuṇa as nonhuman supernatural beings, then their power is domain-specific. However, as unborn, true devotees of God, the nityasūris have a wider scope of power.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Every action that a human performs, every thought and word have multiple witnesses, including the sun and the moon, let alone God who resides in him/her. Any good behaviour (i.e., behaving according to the prescriptions of the scriptures) and every bad behaviour (behaving in contradiction to the scriptures) are recorded and they lead to karma, good and bad respectively.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts

and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Taboos concerning food are many, as food intake is more than for the sake of subsistence.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Respect of sacred objects are a must.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: They care about humans applying divine laws of conduct, whatever field they may pertain to.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of any living being outside the allowed domain is monitored and punished. That of a coreligionist entails worse punishment.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Any unwarranted crime is condemned, as every soul is said to be God's body.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: See previous answer.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Sex should remain within the bounds of what is acceptable (i.e. what is approved of by

scriptures such as Manu-dharma). Sexual practices are also monitored, and lead to bad karma when they happen without the approved boundaries.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: More often than not, it is a bigger sin if the adulterer is a woman. But extramarital physical relations are condemned in general for people desiring piety.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is a big no-no.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Speaking the truth is one of the fundamental requirements of "Hindusim," and this goes beyond the limits of this particular faith.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: This is linked with speaking the truth.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Performing black magic for the sake of harming someone else is frowned upon.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Undue and unjustified fights are frowned upon.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: God, His qualities and acts and His devotees must make up the bulk of any conversation. Malignant gossip is especially to frowned upon, particularly if it has for its object another Śrīvaiṣṇava, and it leads to bad karma.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Fairness is important whatever the field.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: As mentioned in ones of the notes, every thought, word and deed of a human is monitored. And each is supposed tin accordance with scriptures.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: They do on behalf of God, like the planets that affect people's lives.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

Notes: The average human being cannot know all this, although, the fact that God is behind the meting out of justice is not hidden from anyone.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Notes: The reason is not known, especially if one suffers due to the karma acquired in a different birth. Usually sufferings are a result of bad karma, and with the help of astrologers or enlightened people, it is possible to know the cause for one's suffering (bad behaviour, transgression of the religious laws, etc.).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is a means of preventing what is perceived as wayward behaviour and to encourage people to become Śrīvaiṣṇavas, which will end once for all their karma and give them liberation.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: Yes and no. The punishment is proportional to the offence. It could be mild, but it could also be very terrible.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: See previous note.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: This is definitely a possibility. It is said that those who have sinned in their thoughts are born as lower ranking humans, those who have sinned through their words are reborn as animals, and those who have sinned with their bodies are born as trees, etc. But those who have sought refuge at Rāmānuja's feet by becoming Śrīvaiṣṇavas will be spared such a fate, as liberation is guaranteed to them at the end of the bodies.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is a possibility, although I'm yet to come across an example that illustrates this.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The Garuḍa Purāṇa, which is an authoritative text, is made up of lists of punishments that are meted out for the various crimes that are committed. And the punishments are as numerous as the crimes/sins that can be committed.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Punishments in general are emphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different

degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not only this. Punishment can take many forms and can be of different degree of severity.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Notes: The cause can mostly be known by seeking out help of astrologers and/or enlightened people.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The best reward is the liberation of the soul, which reaches God's abode, *Vaikuṅṭha*. This is invariably emphasized.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the *Śrīvaiṣṇavas*, who are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God, thereby liberating their souls from the cycle of birth and death.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated, as the *Śrīvaiṣṇavas* are supposed to reach the heavenly abode of God.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Karma, whether good or bad, obstructs the path to liberation. So rewards other than proximity and service to god and His devotees are not emphasized.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: This is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Many are the rewards that people get in this life for good behaviour. But again, this is mainly for the uninitiated. As for the Śrīvaiṣṇavas, the best reward is serving God and His devotees, and then finally go to His heavenly, where they can continue their task. heavenly abode of God.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This school does believe in the coming of God as Kalki, who is supposed to establish order and justice in this world at the end of Kaliyuga, but there is rarely any emphasis or even mention of this. What is essential for a human being is to behave properly in this birth so that the soul can achieve liberation at death.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Everything is cyclical in this belief system, good follows bad and vice versa. A new, better world will rise after this one that endures the hardships of kaliyuga, but that good world will be destroyed in order to let a bad world come into existence, and so on and so forth.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This religious groups agrees with some texts that are common to other Vedic groups too, e.g. scriptures such as Manu's dharma code.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: For the warrior caste (kṣatriyas), yes.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: Cowardice is a sign of tāmasa ("darkness") quality, hence to be avoided.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: These are qualities that are important in for example the kings. Not a necessary virtue for Śrīvaiṣṇavas. Although nobility of character is a more universal requirement.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: emphasis is on inner beauty, not on the external one, which can make things by making one vain.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: It is only required for those who are in the first stage of life (brahmacarya, during which they do schooling) and for those who have renounced this world (i.e. sanyāsins/ascetics).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Sex is supposed to be practised during specific times under specific conditions according to scriptures such as manu-dharma, mostly within a marriage.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting on days like ekādaśī is supposed to be obligatory for everyone, but it is not limited to this religious group. Renouncers are required to eat less, and fast more.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: It's not a pre-requisite, but it is highly recommended to abstain from certain food items, such as meat, poultry, eggs, but also onion and garlic. More restrictions are applicable for the renouncers, who

are not supposed to eat to satisfy their taste buds.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Bodily alterations: no. Permanent scarring: yes. One of the five rites of initiation requires the symbols of Nārāyana's weapons, the discus and the conch, to be branded on the upper arms of the disciples.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: NB: the acsetics have to give up their material possessions.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Technically-speaking, a disciple is supposed to attend training on important religious meanings from the mentor, but again, it is not a pre-requisite. Although the hagiographic texts do mention disciples serving their ācāryas and attending the lectures, it is not clear whether they all did. Further research is needed in the field.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: While it's not part of the pre-requisites, a disciple is supposed to accept the ethical precepts of the sacred texts, including those of the Vedas and "Vedic" texts, as interpreted by the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: NB: it is noteworthy here that contact with (conversation, sharing food, living with) non-Śrīvaiṣṇavas are discouraged. It is something that is clearly mentioned in Śrīvaiṣṇava texts such as Piḷḷai Lokācārya's Śrīvacanabhūṣaṇam. Within the Śrīvaiṣṇava group, caste rules apply.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Other than what is prescribed by scriptures (such as the sandhyāvandanā for the twice-born), the worship of Nārāyaṇa, as taught by the ācārya during the samāśrayaṇa, is to be done along with the recitation of certain mantras and a set of verses from the canonical texts, the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham. It is not really possible to know more precisely, especially about how things were during the default period.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We have no numbers for this. If public worships happen, then the disciples would have gathered in hundreds. Further research is required on the topic.

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Notes: It is almost impossible to give the number of hours in this case. large-scale events could mean festivals and/or religious functions that happen every fortnight or every month or every

year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

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– Yes

Notes: Please see previous note.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: There are rituals like the sandhyā-vandanā, which are to be performed at specific times of the day. Those kind of rites are synchronised.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: As mentioned earlier, the rite of branding the impressions of God's weapons happens once during initiation. No such practice is repeated after that.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: In the group, the other is referred to as "svāmi" ("Master"); and the individual refers to himself as "aṭiyēṇ" or "dāsan" ("slave"). This is in order to see oneself as unworthy, and a servant of the Lord and his devotees, and to see the others (i.e. the Lord's devotees) as being the masters.

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Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Kings belonging to dynasties such as the Cōḷa, ruled over the land in which this group grew.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Disciples are fed and roofed in places called in specific maṭha-s (literally, hermitages and monasteries, but in practice also rest-houses for the pilgrims) and in places called Rāmānuca-kūṭam-s (rest-houses for the Vaiṣṇava travellers). But there is no mention to my knowledge of institutionalized famine relief. Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. It depends on what that formal education includes. If it is caste-specific, then yes (i.e. Brahmins are taught to be priests in the temples). Otherwise education is open to all (e.g. the education on who God is, what liberation is, how to live and conduct oneself, etc.) and the learning of the Tamil Vedas, the Divya Prabandham.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Once again, some fields are open to both, which is a revolution in a way. The Divya prabandham and its meanings were taught to women too, but the Sanskrit Vedas were restricted to the traivarṇika men, or males who belong to the first three varnas.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: NB: The maṭhas (religious institutions) often depend on external fundings. The disciples are welcome to contribute financially to the well-being of their ācāryas, but this does not mean any taxes or tithes were levied systematically. Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: renouncers are supposed to beg for their food, the people in the monasteries receive donations from chiefs, kings and/or the disciples of the monastery.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Please see previous answer.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Written language, especially in the Tamil-Sanskrit Maṇipravāla, is often the domain of religious professionals, but disciples are also known to write. The script that was used, i.e. grantha--which allowed them to transcribe Sanskrit sounds in Tamil--, may not have been accessible to everyone though.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Although not restricted to religious professionals, it is quite possible that the written language in a particular script was more of the domain of professionals, including scribes.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: NB: it may have used one of the many "Hindu" calendars, with a few exclusive Śrīvaiṣṇava modifications (e.g. how to determine when to fast for the ekādaśī). Further research is required on the topic.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Further research is required on the topic.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Some disciples, especially Brahmins, would have been welcome in Vedic schools, where they learnt to recite the Vedas.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The king may have used a different calendar, which may have been used by the general public, possibly including the Śrīvaiṣṇavas. Further research is required on the topic.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Many teachers, and a few disciples, would have had access to non-religious teachings outside the religious institutions that they belonged to, where they would have learnt for example Tamil literature.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that the king of the region would have organized famine relief, but no such mention is to be found in the texts so far as I know. Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: NB: As citizens of a certain kingdom, the adherents would have received whatever protection the king and his men were willing or capable of giving them.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The pilgrims are fed in the rest-houses; temples feed devotees at certain times of the day. Further research is required on the topic.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that the king provided such relief. Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The "Vedic" codes (as interpreted by the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas) are considered as the legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Being the subjects of a king meant that the adherents were automatically under the control of the king's rules and regulations.

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Kings belonging to dynasties such as the Cōḷa, ruled over the land in which this group grew.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Disciples are fed and roofed in places called in specific maṭha-s (literally, hermitages and monasteries, but in practice also rest-houses for the pilgrims) and in places called Rāmānuca-kūṭam-s (rest-houses for the Vaiṣṇava travellers). But there is no mention to my knowledge of institutionalized famine relief. Further research is required on the topic.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that the king of the region would have organized famine relief, but no such mention is to be found in the texts so far as I know. Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The pilgrims are fed in the rest-houses; temples feed devotees at certain times of the day. Further research is required on the topic.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that the king provided such relief. Further research is required on the topic.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Further research is required on the topic.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Further research is required on the topic.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. It depends on what that formal education includes. If it is caste-specific, then yes (i.e. Brahmins are taught to be priests in the temples). Otherwise education is open to all (e.g. the education on who God is, what liberation is, how to live and conduct oneself, etc.) and the learning of the Tamil Vedas, the Divya Prabandham.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Once again, some fields are open to both, which is a revolution in a way. The Divya prabandham and its meanings were taught to women too, but the Sanskrit Vedas were restricted to the traivarṇika men, or males who belong to the first three varnas.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Some disciples, especially Brahmins, would have been welcome in Vedic schools, where they learnt to recite the Vedas.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: NB: The maṭhas (religious institutions) often depend on external fundings. The disciples are welcome to contribute financially to the well-being of their ācāryas, but this does not mean any taxes or tithes were levied systematically. Further research is required on the topic.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The "Vedic" codes (as interpreted by the Śrīvaiṣṇava ācāryas) are considered as the legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Being the subjects of a king meant that the adherents were automatically under the control of the king's rules and regulations.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: NB: As citizens of a certain kingdom, the adherents would have received whatever protection the king and his men were willing or capable of giving them.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Written language, especially in the Tamil-Sanskrit Maṅḍipravāla, is often the domain of religious professionals, but disciples are also known to write. The script that was used, i.e. grantha--which allowed them to transcribe Sanskrit sounds in Tamil--, may not have been accessible to everyone though.

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Although not restricted to religious professionals, it is quite possible that the written language in a particular script was more of the domain of professionals, including scribes.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Many teachers, and a few disciples, would have had access to non-religious teachings outside the religious institutions that they belonged to, where they would have learnt for example Tamil literature.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: NB: it may have used one of the many "Hindu" calendars, with a few exclusive Śrīvaiṣṇava modifications (e.g. how to determine when to fast for the ekādaśī). Further research is required on the

topic.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The king may have used a different calendar, which may have been used by the general public, possibly including the Śrīvaiṣṇavas. Further research is required on the topic.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: renouncers are supposed to beg for their food, the people in the monasteries receive donations from chiefs, kings and/or the disciples of the monastery.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Please see previous answer.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Further research is required on the topic.